

SITE GPR	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
	2010	B		Min: 62.5734 Max: 62.8226	1203 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 779-783 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: Layer of dirt under 1199

Covered by: SU: 1199 Fills: SU: Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles R <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) R <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth R <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 30% silt 20% sand 50% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
			Compaction	Color
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1199	Covers: Bedrock 1001
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: Layer was black but dried to brown. Excavated with pickaxe & shovel, trowels used to clean bedrock beneath. Hole feature appears to be cut into bedrock & runs under the S excavation limit. Excavated on hot sunny day before lunch.

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: Southwestern corner

Shape: 1/2-oval (irregular; since limits are not original, it's hard to say)

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): No slope

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Some rectangular pieces of tile (noted on drawing below), pieces of ceramic vessels, none clustered.

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Same thickness throughout (~5cm)

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

1203 was sandwiched between 1199 and the bedrock, which appears to have its cracks filled in with tufo rocks/pebbles. We believe that 1203 was accumulated after whatever the bedrock was under was abandoned. The hole feature was only incidentally related to 1203, because it's cut into the bedrock and there was no framing or indication of use around the hole's mouth.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets): 2

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by CAKE ALVB

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PDFd by JFM

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Entered by

on